

FROM FREE SOFTWARE TO OPEN SOURCE: TRAVERSING THE VALUES AND ETHICS OF OPEN SEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

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Once was free software valued for its ‘peculiar form of potentiality’, not per se a thing or technology or license (Kelty 2013) but in the words of Broca, a ‘concrete utopia perhaps’ (2012), something that had possibility. The original values imbued within free software ranged from ‘experimentalism and creativity, provisionality and modifiability, rectification and refraction, dissent and critique, participation and obligation’ (Kelty 2013). Moreover, free software embodied a politics of liberalism, with its roots anchored in Unix, situated within the hybrid academic-corporate culture of Bell-Labs. This was cross-fertilized by nascent computer science departments worldwide, which were critical of software development by corporations, organizations or consultancies (Kelty 2008). At that time, the ethics of open software creation was immanent to academic computer science departments and people came *to* free software as the solution, enacting ‘disruption in the creation, circulation, distribution and control of knowledge’ (Kelty 2013). The power of free software was to make these values, or principles, material and thereby able to be ‘manipulated, reconfigured, tested and torqued’; in other words, radically open to change and promoting process over product as an infrastructural and material strategy for a new world (Kelty 2013).

Yet was Free Software a dispositief (Foucault 2009), or an assemblage (Rabinow 2003), a tactic or an open knowledge infrastructure on its own, or as with open source today, a strategy or underlying practice that is not understood enough? The paper delves into the values and ethics of free software to what is now called, since 1998, ‘open source’, beginning with its negotiations of knowledge and power in regard to intellectual property. Additionally, it investigates the techno-infrastructural reform of ‘the potentiality, modifiability, and portability of the tools and code’ (Kelty 2013) as well as questions of infrastructure, corporate continuity, competition, maintenance and support (Jackson et al. 2011). It traces how Silicon Valley behemoths Google, Facebook, Microsoft, Amazon, Apple are all built on foundations of Linux servers and open source software, networking tools and programming languages. The evolving genre of FOSS (Free Open Source Software) and FLOSS (Free Libre Open Source Software) has been offered as a solution to the problems of (corporate) infrastructure; simultaneously it opens the door to software developers worldwide, who

build new infrastructures and technical solutions based on shared resources and open code.

In order to better understand FOSS, semi-structured ethnographic interviews will be conducted with developers who have been awarded EU funding for NGI (Next Generation Internet) search projects, which have to be made ‘open source’ upon completion. These will address a specific technology, method, tool or problem related to information retrieval, search, indexing, discovery and exploration of information or incorporating search engine evaluation and ethics in search and discovery. This cultural analysis of the domesticated forms open source is taking will contribute to comprehending the values of the search industry and (open) infrastructures. On the one hand it will demonstrate that open source has become an instrumentalized kind of politics, where the power to ‘fork’ the software has disappeared into centralized (closed) knowledge infrastructures and how misnomer companies such as OpenAI, ‘generates within itself the very tools for its analysis, transformation and reconstruction’ (Kelty 2013). On the other, it puts forth the value ‘infrastructuring openness’ applied to interoperability, integration and the construction of ‘recursive publics’ within some of these search projects, going beyond the dominance of conservative-libertarian ideologies.